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An IRT Approach to Assessing Psychometric Properties of the Japanese Version Teacher Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire

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Abstract

This study adapted the Interpersonal Acceptance-Rejection Theory-based Teacher Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire (Child TARQ) for Japanese culture and assessed its psychometric properties. The original 24-item self-report questionnaire measures students' representations of teacher relationships across four dimensions: warmth/affection, hostility/aggression, indifference/neglect, and undifferentiated rejection. Six hundred three Japanese junior high school students (aged 12–15) completed the Japanese Child TARQ and the World Health Organization Five Wellbeing Index (WHO-5-J). Confirmatory factor analysis supported a slightly revised, theoretically sound four-factor model, demonstrating satisfactory construct validity. Utilizing the full graded response model of Item Response Theory, the authors successfully developed an optimized 18-item shortened version of the scale. Test information function curves revealed that this abbreviated form retains equivalent precision and information coverage to the original. Results provided robust support for the internal reliability, convergent validity, and concurrent validity of the shortened TARQ.

Keywords: IRT, Japan, construct validity, teacher acceptance-rejection questionnaire

An IRT Approach to Assessing Psychometric Properties of the Japanese Version Teacher Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire

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Abstract : Interpersonal Acceptance-Rejection Theory (IPARTheory) based Teacher Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire (Child TARQ; Rohner, 2005) is a self-report measure to examine students' representations of relationship with their teacher in terms of warmth/affection (opposite coldness/lack of affection), hostility/aggression, indifference/neglect, and undifferentiated rejection. Purposes of this investigation were to: a) adapt Child TARQ in Japanese culture and evaluate its'construct validity, b) develop a shorter version employing Item Response Theory (IRT) analyses, c) examine the reliability and validity of the shortened version. Six hundred three Japanese junior high school students with ages ranging from 12 through 15 years ($M_{age} = 13.95$, $SD_{age} = 0.85$) responded to the Japanese version of Child TARQ, and the Japanese version of world health organization (WHO) five wellbeing index (WHO-5-J). Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) confirmed a somewhat revised version of the theoretically suggested four-factor model of the Child TARQ. The full graded response (GR) model of the IRT approach resulted in the 18-item shortened version of the Child TARQ. The results provided support for the reliability and preliminary convergent and concurrent validity of the shortened TARQ at the global and subscale level. The Child TARQ is a robust measure in Japan context, and its shortened version is a promising tool for researchers to use with other measures in multivariate studies.

Keywords: IRT, interpersonal acceptance-rejection theory, Japan, teacher acceptance-rejection questionnaire, construct validity

Adolescent pupils stay at school for a considerable amount of time. Their positive or negative experiences at school with teachers have significant

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consequences for their development across social, emotional, behavioral, and academic domains (McGrath & Bergen, 2015; Özdemir & Özdemir, 2020). During the past decades, there has been an expanding interest in the association between satisfaction of need for positive response or perceived acceptance from teachers and adolescents' social-emotional, behavioral functioning, and adjustment (Ali, Khaleque & Rohner, 2015; Rohner, 2010). Such perceived positive response or acceptance in terms of care, involvement, support, nurturance and conversely rejection in terms of hostility, neglect, and lack of care that student experiences from teacher can be measured by a promising questionnaire—the Teacher Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire (TARQ: Child) (Rohner, 2005). However, there is no psychometric information on the TARQ except reliability information. The current study aimed to adapt TARQ and examine the construct validity and reliability on Japanese adolescents and to develop a brief version of TARQ that gives similar precision as the original one that can easily be used in multivariate studies.

TARQ is a self-report questionnaire and has a sound theoretical basis since it was devised on the well-established, evidence-based Interpersonal Acceptance-rejection theory (IPARTheory) (Rohner, 1986, 2019). The 24-item TARQ was adapted from the Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire (PARQ). In line with IPARTheory, the four-factor Child TARQ was designed to ask children to indicate the degree of warmth or affection (with the opposite being coldness/lack of affection), hostility/aggression, indifference/neglect, and undifferentiated rejection they perceive from teachers. (1) The warmth/affection factor refers to the teacher-student relationship in which teachers are perceived as either nurturing, emotionally supportive, and caring or affectively cold or unaffectionate. (2) The hostility/aggression factor indicates that teacher-student relations in which teachers are perceived to express aggression (i.e., either physical or verbal aggression or both), enmity, annoyance, or resentment toward students. (3) indifference/neglect factor refers to the teacher-student relationship in which teachers are perceived as lacking concern about their students' different needs. Finally, (4) the undifferentiated rejection factor refers to teacher-student relationships in which teachers are perceived as uncaring, unaffectionate, unloving, and unappreciative towards students, inspite of having no apparent behavioral indications that they are unaffectionate, aggressive, neglectful or rejecting. The Child TARQ has been applied in six cross-cultural studies—Bangladesh (Rohner, Khaleque, Elias, & Sultana, 2010), Estonia (Tulviste & Rohner, 2010), India (Parmar & Rohner, 2010), Kuwait (Rohner, Parmar, & Ibrahim, 2010), Turkey (Erkman, Caner, Sart, Börkan, & Sahan, 2010), and the USA (Khan, Haynes, Armstrong, & Rohner, 2010) to evaluate the

associations between teacher acceptance-rejection and students' outcomes. However, psychometric properties have not been sufficiently confirmed, the examination of its construct validity through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), which may provide evidence whether TARQ reflects theoretically proposed four-factor structures was overlooked in previous studies. The advantages of such validation work of Child TARQ will contribute to conduct sound and valid research addressing teacher acceptance-rejection. In turn, students' representations of teacher acceptance-rejection form a substantial area of interest in the field of teacher-student relationship and students' psychological and academic outcome.

Previous literature exhibited that the global scale of TARQ has sufficient internal consistency in different cultures. The coefficient alphas of the global TARQ for Bangladeshi, Estonian, Indian, and Turkish adolescents were .85, .91, .88, .84 respectively (Erkman et al., 2010; Parmar & Rohner, 2010; Rohner, et al., 2010; Tulviste & Rohner, 2010). Nevertheless, evidence of reliability in the subscale level is absent in the literature.

To optimally shorten an existing measure and to assess the efficacy of the shortened scale for especial samples such as children, adolescents, or ill patients, IRT analysis is a recommended approach to allow quick assessment and to reduce response burden, to increase the feasibility of conducting researches (Edelen & Reeve, 2007; Gordon, 2015). The present study undertook the item response theory (IRT) approach to choose the most useful items for developing a shortened TARQ that will be analogs as the original one in terms of precision of information and to make future studies feasible on Japanese children focusing on teacher acceptance-rejection accompanying with other multi-item measures. Notably, researchers in Japan working with children and adolescents have recently been confronting dilemmas and challenges in conducting field research and data collection. On the one hand, school authorities and parents are becoming very restrictive and strict about permitting researchers to collect data from their children. If any researchers obtain permission from authorities, they need to strictly follow certain thresholds for the length of a questionnaire to minimize response burden. On the other hand, research questions are becoming progressively complex and demanding the administration of a number of scales altogether. In these circumstances, the length of the Child TARQ is an issue; a shorter and valid scale that maintains the precision and scope of the original is needed.

IRT approach has advantages in reducing a measure as it can evaluate the amount of information offered by each item on the continuum of the latent trait through the item information function (IIF). It is possible to measure the trait level

with precision if the amount of information is large, produced by an item. If the amount of information is minuscule, the underlying trait estimation cannot precisely be measured. Consequently, an optimally shortened measure can be developed by selecting the best performing items (i.e., those items offer sufficient information throughout the latent trait continuum).

Furthermore, the IRT approach has another benefit to compare the shortened and original tools by producing the test information functions (TIF), and the TIFs evaluate (a) the accuracy of the scales at various levels of a measured trait rather than demonstrating a single value of reliability (e.g., Cronbach's α) (Embretson & Reise, 2000); (b) whether the shortened scale carries the analogous information as the original one (Chiesi, Morsanyi, Donati, & Primi, 2018). Another advantage of using IRT models is that they also allow the assessment of the concordance between the obtained scores of an original and its shortened version (Edelen & Reeve, 2007; Lozano, Diaz-Batanero, Rojas, & Pilatti, 2018).

In this study, we were interested in Japanese junior high school students, as they pass a long time every day in their schools and are likely to have a wider scope of interactions with teachers than students in other countries (Trembl, 2001). The Japanese education system is more teacher-centered (Fukuzawa, 1994). Students' perceived teacher support has been identified as a major predictor of depression or emotional maladjustment among Japanese adolescents (Mizuta, Suzuki, Yamagata, & Ojima, 2017). Evaluating the construct validity and developing an abbreviated version of TARQ may significantly stimulate future studies in Japan to explore how perceived teacher acceptance-rejection in terms of coldness/lack of affection, hostility/aggression, indifference/neglect, and undifferentiated rejection may impact adolescents' wellbeing and adjustment.

The Current Study

We had four purposes in this study. First, we aimed to adapt Child TARQ in Japanese culture and evaluate its construct validity through CFA. This is the first study to assess the construct validity of the Child TARQ. To recall, in literature, construct validity as to what extent a psychological instrument measures the concept it expects to measure (Brown, 2015). CFA is the most commonly used and recommended approach for evaluating the construct validity if there is a theory or prior hypothesis (Brown, 2015; Kline, 2005). In the evaluation of construct validity, we expect that the Japanese version of the TARQ will have a similar 4-factor model as theoretically proposed (Hypothesis 1). Furthermore, we kept open the way for possible testing a higher-order single factor model by loading the 4-factor model

to a single higher-order factor, if suggested by the CFA as appropriate for Child TARQ. To get strong evidence of construct validity for each factor of TARQ, we additionally investigated the construct convergent validity (Churchill, 1979). It refers to the extent to which a cluster of items demonstrates to be an indicator of a single latent construct. To determine the construct convergent validity, three complementary criteria were used as suggested by Morawska, Sanders, Haslam, Filus, and Fletcher (2014; see data analysis part for details).

Second, after getting a validated version of TARQ, we proceeded to the second objective, i.e., to devise a shortened form of the Japanese Child TARQ with the same properties as the original questionnaire. We expect that selection of restricted number of items in the item pool will permit quick assessment and reduce response burden, study cost, and increase the feasibility of conducting researches on children (Edelen & Reeve, 2007; Gordon, 2015). Following the recommendations of Marsh, Hau, Balla, and Grayson (1998), we intended to select a minimum of sixteen items (i.e., at least four items for each factor) as theoretically 24-item TARQ has 4-factors. So, the 4-item undifferentiated rejection dimension of TARQ was not considered for reducing any item.

Third, we examined the preliminary validity of the shortened TARQ by investigating convergent validity and concurrent validity. For investigating the convergent validity, we computed correlations between the IRT scores (generated for each respondent in each subscale) of the shortened and original length Child TARQ. If the correlation between them were higher than .80, we considered that the construct has convergent validity (Brown, 2015). To assess the concurrent validity of the shortened Japanese version TARQ, we evaluated the relationships between shortened TARQ (global scale and 4 subscales) and the Japanese version world health organization (WHO) five wellbeing index (WHO-5-J; Awata et al., 2007). In a meta-analysis, it was evident that the global score of TARQ was significantly associated with the Child Personality Assessment Questionnaire (PAQ) – which total score measures children's self-reported overall (mal)adjustment (Ali et al., 2015). Review studies also suggested the association between negative teacher-student relationships and student mental health problems such as depressive symptoms, aggression, anxiety, and other psychological problems (Dods, 2013; Krane, Karlsson, Ness, & Kim, 2016). Some findings showed that students' perception of being openly humiliated, labeling, and punished by teachers negatively impacts their wellbeing (McGrath & Bergen, 2015; Muller, 2001). Therefore, these findings increase the likelihood that shortened TARQ scores will be negatively correlated with the scores of WHO-5-J (Hypothesis 2).

Fourth, we aimed to examine and compare the internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) (Cronbach, 1951) and the latent construct reliability (H coefficient) (Hancock & Mueller, 2001) of the two versions (shortened and original). Previous literature showed that the global scale of TARQ has satisfactory internal consistency. However, findings of internal consistencies for each sub-scale were absent in the literature. Thus, this study aimed to demonstrate the first time the Cronbach's alpha and H coefficient for TARQ in sub-scale level. Notably, the violation of the assumption of uncorrelated errors and tau-equivalence may result in biased Cronbach's alpha (Cheng, Yuan, & Liu, 2012). The H coefficient can overcome these limitations. H coefficient has advantages because it produces estimates based on the weights of the individual items to measure the latent construct. The interpretation and range of these coefficient estimates are the same as those of Cronbach's alpha (Hancock & Mueller, 2001). We expected that both versions of the global TARQ (shortened and original) would demonstrate good internal consistency (Hypothesis 3). We could not formulate any Hypothesis regarding the consistency of TARQ on the subscale level.

Methods

Participants

Primarily 869 Japanese junior high school students were conveniently recruited online throughout Japan, using a Japanese research company (see the procedure for details). However, we eliminated: (a) 216 participants for incorrect responses in the attention check items (see measures for details) and (b) 50 respondents for withdrawal of consent. The final sample comprised of 603 adolescents (237 girls, 366 boys) between 12 and 15 years of age ($M = 13.95$ years and $SD_{age} = 0.85$). Participants were students of first grade (32%), second grade (35%), and third grade (33%) in junior high schools. About 38%, 21%, and 16% of the participants lived in the Kanto (eastern Japan), Kansai (west-central Japan), and Chubu (central Japan) metropolitan regions, respectively. The remaining 25% participants lived in the Hokkaido, Tohoku, Chugoku, Shikoku, and Kyushu regions that are comparatively rural areas than to the Kanto, Kansai, and Chubu regions.

Procedures

Ethical approval was granted from the Graduate School of Education and Human Development, Nagoya University, before the commencement of the study. As there was no previous Japanese version of Child TARQ, we started the adaptation process of Child TARQ into the Japanese language after getting permission from

Professor Ronald P. Rohner, the original author. Child TARQ was adapted into the Japanese language and culture through forward, and back-translations. A panel of experts (consists of a professor of life-span developmental psychology, forward translators—two graduate students of psychology, back translator—bilingual expert at English & Japanese, and an assistant professor of psychology) synthesized, judged, and compared the adapted version in forward and back-translation phases. Furthermore, in the process of improving the translation, we requested two school teachers to provide their suggestions based their experience in dealing with their students. Later, few words were adjusted following their recommendations.

We collected data through a research company, NTT Com Online Marketing Solutions Co. Ltd. (<https://www.nttcoms.com/>). First, the company advertised online the link of the survey for parents who are company monitors. The research company targeted first parents as our required sample was minor. They informed parents about the purposes as well as the detailed protocol of the study. Parents who provided consent for their children's participation obtained a URL link of the questionnaire and they were requested to forward it to their children. Next, the children who accessed the link were informed about the study along with the ethical details, only who gave assent participated in this investigation.

Measures

The participants answered self-report measures and a personal information form (PIF) that elicited demographic information (i.e., age, sex, and grade in school).

Child TARQ. It is a self-report questionnaire of 24 items (Rohner, 2005) that asks children to report the level of acceptance and rejection they come across from the teacher to whom s/he feels more attached in school. As mentioned earlier, this measure consists of four sub-scales: (a) Hostility/aggression (H/A) (e.g., my teacher says many unkind things to me; 6 items), (b) indifference/neglect (I/N) (e.g., my teacher pays no attention to me; 6 items), (c) undifferentiated rejection (UR) (e.g., my teacher seems to dislike me; 4 items) and (d) warmth/affectionate (e.g., says nice things about me; 8 items). The warmth/affection subscale was reversely scored to indicate coldness/lack of affection (C/LA). Items are scored on a 4-point Likert-type scale from 4 (*almost always true*) to 1 (*almost never true*). Higher scores on the TARQ reveal individuals' perceptions of increasing rejection. Information about the reliabilities of this study has been reported in the result section.

WHO-5-J. The WHO-5- J (Awata et al., 2007) was used to assess the mental wellbeing of adolescents. The WHO-5 (1998) is a unidimensional 5-item brief

questionnaire. The items are positively phrased (i.e., “I have felt cheerful and in good spirits”). Participants were asked to respond to these items in 0 (*at no time*) to 5 (*all of the time*) point scales considering feelings over the last two weeks. The raw scores were transformed into a score ranging from 0 (worst thinkable wellbeing) to 100 (best thinkable wellbeing).

The global measure of wellbeing was applied to children and adolescents in several studies and demonstrated satisfactory reliability and validity (Allgaier et al., 2012). In this study, for this scale coefficient alpha was .92.

Attention check items. Three items were used to identify unengaged respondents. These items (i.e., “please skip this item and move on,” “to show that you are reading this sentence carefully, please select the option *almost never true*,” “If you are reading the sentence carefully, please select the option *rarely true*”) were embedded within the blocks of main items of the questionnaires. Respondents who failed in any of the three items were not included in the sample.

Data Analyses

The factor structure of TARQ was examined via CFA in order to assess the construct validity. To evaluate the *construct convergent validity*, three complementary criteria have been used: (1) the significance and the extent of factor loadings, (2) the average variance extracted (AVE) estimates between the latent factors and minimum 50% (AVE > 50%) variance than error is desired, and (3) the estimates of the composite reliability (CR), and coefficient more than .70 indicate satisfactory construct convergent validity (Morawska et al., 2014).

For selecting items for the short version, we used the item information function criteria generated by the item slope and threshold parameters based on IRT. We generated the item information function (IIF) curve for each item that demonstrates the amount and distribution of information an item delivers on the latent attitude continuum (θ) graphically. Besides, we checked the test information functions (TIF) to keep (generated by aggregating all IIF on a single item) the shortened version alike with the original length scale. We calibrated IRT using the IRTPRO (Item Response Theory for Patient-Reported Outcomes) version 4.2 (student version) (Cai, Thissen, & du Toit, 2017). The graded response (GR) model (Samejima, 1969), a commonly used and most appropriate model for ordered response categories (Likert-type item responses) was used (Edelen & Reeve 2007; Toland, 2014). We examined the good range of the slope parameter which is 0.5 or higher in ordered polytomous items following the guidelines by Baker (2001) and Toland (2014). We examined item threshold parameters following Toland’s (2014)

guidelines of the ideal threshold range (-3 to +3). Before choosing an IRT model (full GR model — considers individual slope parameter for an individual item in the model, or parsimonious GR model — considers a common slope parameter for all items), the unidimensionality and local independence assumptions were evaluated for each subscale of TARQ using the CFA procedure. We considered the unidimensionality assumption was achieved when there was a good model fit. Local independence can be assumed when pair-wise residual correlation was $\leq .20$ (Morizot, Ainsworth, & Reise, 2007).

To keep consistency in the analyses between IRT and CFA, all the CFA analyses (e.g. factor structure for construct validity and unidimensionality assumption) were conducted in this study using Mplus v.8.4 software (Muthén & Muthén, 1998-2017), employing the weighted least square mean and variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimator. This robust estimator is recommended for ordered categorical data. As large sample size could influence WLSMV χ^2 values, we evaluated the overall model fit by assessing the comparative fit index (CFI), the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR), and the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA). The *acceptable fit* was considered when $CFI \geq .90$, $SRMR \leq .08$, and $RMSEA \leq .10$ (Brown, 2015; Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2014; Hu & Bentler, 1999; MacCallum, Browne, & Sugawara, 1996).

Results

Construct Validity of the Child TARQ

Theoretically proposed 4-factor model showed a very marginal model fit. On account of this, we inspected the modification indices of this model which suggested that item 13 (a positively worded item [pays a lot of attention to me] of I/N subscale) was strongly associated with C/LA (items of this scale are positively worded) (see appendix for the item details). Given this finding, we revised the 4-factor model by loading item 13 on the C/LA factor. Consequently, the revised 4-factor model showed a much better improvement to the fit indices. Considering the relative magnitude of the correlations between the revised 4-latent factors (see Figure 1), we tested support for the higher-order single factor model by loading the revised 4-factor model to a single higher-order factor. Although the higher-order single factor model showed an acceptable fit but indicated less model fit to the data than to the revised 4-factor model (see Table 1). In summary, the revised 4-factor model explained much more precise relationships among the indicators, thereby supports the construct validity (see Figure 1). This model was considered in further analyses.

In the results of *construct convergent validity*, all indicators of the Child TARQ had significant satisfactory factor loadings on respective factors (see Figure 1). The AVE values (.662 in C/LA, .601 in H/A, .631 in I/N, .680 in UR) and CR estimates (.904 in C/LA, .897 in H/A, .895 both in I/N, and UR) of all factors exceeded the minimum desired cut-off values.

IRT Analyses to Develop a Shortened Version of the Child TARQ

Basic descriptive. We identified that only a few students endorsed the highest response category (i.e., option 4, *almost always true*, that denotes rejection) of most of the items (after reverse scoring the positively stated item). Very few participants (6%, $n = 36$) selected the option 4 across 24 items. We stated earlier that TARQ was derived from PARQ. For samples from the general population, it is not uncommon that the scores of PARQ are positively skewed (i.e., the majority of the participants experienced less rejection). For TARQ, participants also responded in a similar pattern. To increase the accuracy of item parameter estimation of IRT analysis, we combined the responses of option three and option four into one category following the suggestions of Edelen and Reeve (2007), and Toland (2014).

To assess the appropriateness of performing IRT analysis with 3-category, we further compared descriptive statistics (M , SD), item-total correlations, Cronbach's α , and the Fisher's z -transformed average inter-item correlations of the 3-category (combined category) and 4-category (original category) version of each subscale of the Child TARQ following the guidelines by Edelen and Reeve (2007). We found the 4-category and 3-category versions of the Child TARQ was comparable in terms of the item-total correlations and the Fisher's z -transformed average inter-item correlations, descriptive statistics (M , SD), and Cronbach's α . Thus, we designated to analyze and report the 3-category version of Child TARQ in detail.

Unidimensionality and local independence assumption testing. We performed the single factor CFA for each subscale of the Child TARQ to test the unidimensionality and local independence assumption. We found that single factor C/LA, H/A, I/N except UR showed acceptable fit (C/LA: $\chi^2_{\text{WLSMV}}(27) = 93.15$, $p < .001$; CFI = .995; SRMR = .020; RMSEA = .064; H/A: $\chi^2_{\text{WLSMV}}(9) = 28.67$, $p < .001$; CFI = .994; SRMR = .038; RMSEA = .060; I/N: $\chi^2_{\text{WLSMV}}(5) = 13.08$, $p = .05$; CFI = .998; SRMR = .016; RMSEA = .052; UR: $\chi^2_{\text{WLSMV}}(2) = 36.06$, $p < .001$; CFI = .98; SRMR = .025; RMSEA = .16) and their pair-wise item residual correlation matrices were $\leq .20$. Thus, unidimensionality and local independence were met in C/LA, H/A, I/N subscale of Child TARQ. The misfit UR model will not affect the result as we did consider removal of any items from UR.

Table 1
 Confirmatory Factor Analysis of the Factor Structure of the 24-item Japanese Version of Child TARQ

Model	χ^2 (WLSMV)	$\Delta\chi^2$ (WLSMV)	df	Δdf	CFI	SRMR	RMSEA	RMSEA 90% CI
4-factor model	1645.48***	----	246	----	.924	.067	.097	.093-.10
4-factor model (revised)	954.16***	----	246	----	.962	.052	.069	.064-.074
Higher order single factor model	1031.79***	----	248	----	.958	.055	.072	.068-.077
Higher order single factor model vs. 4-factor model (revised)		42.30***		2				

Note. χ^2 (WLSMV) = Chi-square of weighted least square mean variance adjusted estimator; *df* = degrees of freedom; CFI = comparative fit index; SRMR = standardized root mean square residual; RMSEA = root mean square error of approximation; CI = confidence interval; ****p* < .001.

Figure 1. Revised 4-factor model of the 24-item Japanese version of Child TARQ. Standardized values are reported.*** $p < .001$

IRT calibration. Evaluation of the model fit of the IRT analysis of the two GR models was estimated and compared through multiple fit indices. Following guidelines of Toland (2014), we considered 2 log-likelihood, AIC and BIC statistics (smaller values indicate better model fit), M_2 limited information goodness-of-fit statistic (smaller value better model fit) and RMSEA index (preferred model fit is similar with as defined in SEM) for model fit. The significant LRT for each subscale (C/LA: LRT = 32.26, $df = 8$, $p < .001$; H/A: LRT = 138.31, $df = 5$, $p < .001$; I/N: LRT = 49.67, $df = 4$, $p < .001$; UR: LRT = 10.16, $df = 3$, $p = .17$) indicated that further complexity of the full GR models (permitting slope parameter to vary across items) were required to raise model fit over those found with the parsimonious GR models. Also, in terms of other model fit indices of IRT, the full GR model showed better model fit than those of the parsimonious GR model (See Table 2 for details) for the Child TARQ. Thus, the parameters (slopes and thresholds) of the item of the full GR model were explained in the next point.

Items properties of the Child TARQ in their designated subscale reflected (see Table 3) good range but substantial variation in the discrimination/slope values

(C/LA: $a = 2.23$ to 3.82 ; H/A: $a = 1.11$ to 4.80 ; I/N: $a = 1.78$ to 3.89 ; UR: $a = 2.34$ to 3.89). The threshold/difficulty parameters showed an ample range of the underlying construct (C/LA: $b = -1.29$ to 1.62 ; H/A: $b = -0.69$ to 2.16 ; I/N $b = -0.47$ to 1.97 ; UR: $b = .07$ to 1.87). We also checked item-level fit, adopting summed score item fit statistics ($S-\chi^2$), with a 1% significance level. Two items per subscale were identified as a misfit at $p < .01$, however, the removal of misfit items may reduce the scale reliability and may affect the content validity (Zhao & Hambleton, 2017). As retaining the misfit items may have a negligible impact on score estimation (Zhao, 2017); besides, it is also necessary to keep adequate content coverage (Zhao & Hambleton, 2017) to select items for making a shortened version. Thus, we did consider the misfit items.

Item selection for the shortened version. We shortened the Child TARQ maintaining a reasonable balance of the content and Following the minimum 4 item keeping criteria. We selected six items (19,13, 22, 17, 12, 24) in C/LA, four items (14, 10, 4, 18) in H/A, four items (11, 7, 2, 23) in I/N subscale and all items of UR (8, 5, 21, 16) for the shortened version following the highest IIF criteria (See Figure 2).

To compare whether the shortened TARQ giving comparable information as the original length TARQ, the test information function (TIF) curves of the shortened scale and original length TARQ in each subscale were generated (See Figure 3). Figure 3 depicting the test information function (TIF) curves of the shortened version had a representative and equivalent shape and coverage of total information as to those of the original version Child TARQ.

Preliminary Validity Evidence of the Shortened Japanese Version of the Child TARQ

The correlation coefficient of the IRT scores of the shortened and the original version were .985 (C/LA), .931 (H/A), and .986 (I/N) with $p < .01$, which indicate satisfactory *convergent validity* of the shortened Child TARQ. Moreover, no significant mean difference emerged for each pair of the original and shortened scales.

The correlation coefficients between shortened TARQ (overall score and four subscales' scores) and the WHO-5-J were all significant, and all the correlations being negative (Overall TARQ and WHO-5-J: $r = -.345$, $p < .01$; C/LA and WHO-5-J: $r = -.338$, $p < .01$; H/A and WHO-5-J: $r = -.125$, $p < .01$; I/N and WHO-5-J: $r = -.327$, $p < .01$; UR and WHO-5-J: $r = -.294$, $p < .01$). These findings confirmed the concurrent validity of the shortened TARQ.

Table 2
Model Fit Statistic of Full GR Model and Parsimonious GR Model of the Child TARQ

Subscales	Full GR model					Parsimonious GR model						
	M_2	df	RMSEA	-2LL	AIC	BIC	M_2	df	RMSEA	-2LL	AIC	BIC
Coldness/ lack of affection	487.22***	135	.07	6921.59	6975.59	7094.44	517.58***	143	.07	6953.85	6991.85	7075.48
Hostility/ aggression	184.10***	54	.06	4596.91	4632.91	4712.14	371.40***	59	.09	4735.22	4761.22	4818.45
Indifference/ neglect	207.62***	35	.09	4715.33	4745.33	4811.36	259.02***	39	.10	4765.00	4787.00	4835.42
Undifferentiated rejection	143.19***	20	.10	3374.02	3398.02	3450.84	151.59***	23	.10	3384.18	3402.18	3441.80

Note. GR=Graded Response; M_2 = limited information overall goodness of fit statistic; df = degrees of freedom; RMSEA = root mean square error of approximation; -2LL = -2 log likelihood; AIC = Akaike information criterion; BIC = Bayesian information criterion.
 *** $p < .001$.

Table 3
Results of Item Parameter Estimates of GR Model of TARQ

Items	Slope (discrimination)	Item threshold	
	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i> ₁	<i>b</i> ₂
Coldness/lack of affection			
Item 1	2.23 (.19)	-1.09 (.09)	1.62 (.11)
Item 3	2.43 (.19)	-1.29 (.09)	0.75 (.07)
Item 9	2.72 (.22)	-1.26 (.09)	0.90 (.07)
Item 12	3.00 (.25)	-1.26 (.08)	0.60 (.06)
Item 13	3.27 (.28)	-1.09 (.08)	0.97 (.07)
Item 17	3.06 (.25)	-1.01 (.07)	0.85 (.07)
Item 19	3.82 (.35)	-0.77 (.06)	1.07 (.07)
Item 22	3.16 (.27)	-1.28 (.08)	0.55 (.06)
Item 24	2.78 (.23)	-0.72 (.07)	1.39 (.09)
Hostility/aggression			
Item 4	3.31 (.48)	1.46 (.09)	2.16 (.16)
Item 6	1.32 (.14)	-0.22 (.08)	1.35 (.13)
Item 10	4.56 (.65)	0.89 (.06)	1.96 (.12)
Item 14	4.80 (.66)	0.79 (.06)	1.84 (.11)
Item 18	2.17 (.22)	0.60 (.07)	1.85 (.14)
Item 20	1.11 (.13)	-0.69 (.11)	1.73 (.18)
Indifference/neglect			
Item 2	2.24 (.20)	-0.47 (.07)	1.42 (.10)
Item 7	3.20 (.33)	-0.10 (.06)	1.27 (.08)
Item 11	3.89 (.48)	-0.08 (.06)	1.37 (.08)
Item 15	1.90 (.17)	-0.32 (.07)	1.42 (.10)
Item 23	1.78 (.17)	0.21 (.07)	1.97 (.15)
Undifferentiated rejection			
Item 5	2.94 (.32)	0.42 (.06)	1.53 (.10)
Item 8	3.89 (.52)	0.07 (.06)	1.72 (.10)
Item 16	2.34 (.23)	0.20 (.06)	1.84 (.12)
Item 21	2.44 (.25)	0.19 (.06)	1.87 (.12)

Note. GR = graded response. Values in parenthesis are item parameter standard error estimate. Bold indicates the items those were selected for the shortened Form.

Figure 2. Item Information Function (IIF) curves of Child TARQ. Each curve represents the amount of information (Y-axis) each item provides over the θ range (X-axis). The IIF curves for the items of coldness/lack of affection are depicted in 2a; The IIF curves for items of hostility/ aggression are depicted in 2b; IIF curves for the items of indifference/neglect are depicted in 2c; IIF curves for items of undifferentiated rejection are depicted in 2d.

Figure 3. Total Information Function (TIF) curve of Child TARQ. TIF curves of coldness/ lack of affection are depicted in 3a; TIF curves of hostility/ aggression are depicted in 3b; TIF curves of indifference/ neglect are depicted in 3c. Solid lines = original 24-item TARQ, Dashed lines = 18-item shortened Child TARQ. The X-axis represents the latent variable (θ), perceived teacher rejection (coldness, hostility, indifference). The Y-axis represents the amount of information provided by the subscales for a given score.

Reliability

It is clear from Table 4 that the global scale and all sub scales of the original and shortened form of the Child TARQ had acceptable to excellent reliabilities, and reducing items in Child TARQ did not affect its consistencies.

Table 4
Reliability of the Original Form and Shortened Form of Child TARQ

Scales	Coefficient <i>H</i>		Cronbach α	
	Original form	Shortened form	Original form	Shortened form
Child TARQ			.93	.93
Coldness/Lack of affection	.95	.93	.91	.89
Hostility/Aggression	.94	.95	.76	.81
Indifference/Neglect	.90	.89	.83	.82
Undifferentiated rejection	.91	.91	.82	.82

Discussion

The purposes of this study were to: (a) adapt Child TARQ and evaluate its construct validity on Japanese adolescents, (b) develop a brief version of this measure which gives similar information as the original one, and (c) assess the preliminary validity of the shortened version and finally to determine the consistencies both for the shortened and original version of Japanese TARQ.

Our study is the first of its kind to report the construct validity of Child TARQ through CFA. The CFA results indicated a marginal model fit for the theoretically proposed four-factor oblique model. In contrast, there was support for a slightly revised 4-factor model where item 13 (a positively worded item of the I/Nfactor), loaded on the C/LA factor (all items of this factor are also positively worded). Previous literature has reported that the positive and negative items are prone to load on different factors. For example, Gomez and Suhaimi (2014) and Dedeler, Akun, & Batigun (2017) found that positively and negatively phrased items on the PARQ (with item content similar to that of the Child TARQ) loaded on separate factors. Additionally tested the higher-order factor model exhibited an acceptable fit but less fit than the revised 4-factor model. Therefore, hypothesis 1 was partially supported. The construct convergent validity was determined by examining the factor loadings, CR estimates, and AVEs of the individual factors. The Japanese version of the Child TARQ had adequate construct convergent validity

in terms of significant and satisfactory factor loadings for all items, good composite reliability estimates for all four individual factors, and satisfactory AVE values for all factors.

The short form has been constructed based on IRT. We expected that shortening the Child TARQ would facilitate an increase in the practical utility of the questionnaire for participants' engagement. Besides, it would promote a broader scope of data collection from Japanese adolescents by incorporating additional constructs.

Performing a series of unidimensional IRT analyses based on the GR model on the individual subscales of the Child TARQ, we found that the discriminating or slope parameters of the Child TARQ demonstrated a good ability to discriminate between people with higher and lower levels of perceived rejection. There were significant variations among items based on the slope parameters that reflect the strength of each item's relationship with the latent variable. The location/threshold parameters indicated that together, the items of the Child TARQ were more useful in identifying adolescents who perceived average to high levels of rejection from their teachers. We adopted item information criteria to select more information-providing items, and this approach resulted in 18 items for the shortened TARQ. Thus, the shortened Child TARQ commensurate with the original-length scale regarding the shape and coverage of information according to the TIF curves.

This investigation also offers preliminary support for the validity of the shortened TARQ. This study confirms the convergent validity, exhibiting the concordance between the IRT scores (θ s) of the four sub-scales (C/LA, HA, I/N) of the original and shortened versions. In addition, the intra-scale correlations demonstrated the same direction as well as a substantial concordance. As expected, the shortened TARQ, including its four sub-scales, showed adequate concurrent validity by demonstrating significant correlations with the WHO-5-J. Thus, hypothesis 2 was supported. This result is in similar line with IPARTheory (Rohner, 2005) and previous empirical evidence (Rohner, 2010) that showed that TARQ is significantly associated with the adolescents' psychological health related measures.

This study is the first to report the internal consistencies (Cronbach's alphas) for the Japanese version both on the global scale level and subscale level. We also first report the latent construct reliability (H coefficient) for TARQ for each subscale. We compared the Cronbach's alphas and H coefficients both for the original and shortened Japanese versions. As expected, the global scale of the original and shortened TARQ showed excellent internal consistencies. Thus,

Hypothesis 3 was supported. These findings on the Child TARQ in the Japanese context are in line with those of past studies conducted in six countries, which reported that the Child TARQ is a psychometrically reliable measure for school-going children (e.g., Rohner, 2010). The internal consistency estimates and *H* coefficients of the subscales of the original version and shortened version were excellent. Notably, reducing the 24-item original Japanese version to the 18-item shortened version did not affect its internal consistency.

There were a number of implications in this study. This study is the first to examine the construct validity of Child TARQ. This study contributes to the literature on IPARTheory, as we first examined the factor structure of the Child TARQ and proposed a slightly revised four-factor model that could better explain the dimensions of teacher acceptance-rejection for Japanese adolescents. Another finding in the current study is worthy of note, a higher order model (loaded the revised four factors onto a single higher-order factor) also exhibited acceptable fit. Thus, it is also appropriate to capture a unidimensional construct of teacher acceptance-rejection by computing a total score or yielding a latent construct from all 4-factors. We also first reported the construct convergent validity of TARQ that also added strong evidence of the validity of TARQ. We propose that the proposed four-factor model could have a better model fit if item 13 of the Child TARQ were rewritten to be a negatively worded item. In this study, we analyzed the detailed item-level and model parameters of the Child TARQ utilizing the IRT approach in the literature of IPARTheory first time, which provided complete information about the precision of the Child TARQ along with the latent attitude continuum. The shortened version of TARQ captures similar psychometric properties as the original one and could make feasible future studies on teacher acceptance-rejection and adolescents' development. Moreover, a shortened version could boost children's participation by making the scale less time consuming and more economical especially in extensive protocols, if applied with other interpersonal acceptance-rejection related measure to holistically understand the role of interpersonal (paternal, maternal, teacher, and peer) on adolescents' developmental outcomes. This study provided a better account of the reliability results of the original and shortened TARQ both at the global and subscale level. Finally, we have also reported preliminary external validity results of the shortened TARQ on the subscale level. All factors of shortened TARQ appear relevant to students' psychological health, suggesting that students' perceived teacher acceptance-rejection during the middle school years has a great significance for educators, parents, as well as school mental health professionals.

Several limitations must be noted that highlight the necessity for future research. First, the Japanese version of the Child TARQ has satisfactory construct validity. However, further studies are needed to examine the construct validity (convergent and discriminant validity) of the Child TARQ with other already validated similar or different scales in Japanese culture. Second, the preliminary evidence on the validity of the shortened version of the Japanese Child TARQ was collected from the same sample due to time and economic constraints, and the restrictions on surveying Japanese children also undermined the opportunity for data collection. Future studies should fully validate the shortened version of the Japanese Child TARQ. Despite the aforesaid limitations, this study demonstrates the robustness of the Child TARQ in Japan context. Researchers, psychologists, and educators need valid but brief measures that can tap perceived acceptance-rejection from teacher. We suggest the shortened Child TARQ as a promising tool to be used by researchers or professionals in extensive protocols and the quick assessment of perceived teacher acceptance-rejection.

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Appendix
Items of Child TARQ

My teacher

1. Says nice things about me
2. **Pays no attention to me**
3. Makes it easy for me to tell things that are important to me
4. **Hits me, even when I do not deserve it**
5. **Sees me as a big nuisance**
6. Punishes me severely when s(he) is angry
7. **Is too busy to answer my questions**
8. **Seems to dislike me**
9. Is really interested in what I do
10. **Says many unkind things to me**
11. **Pays no attention when I ask for help**
12. **Makes me feel wanted and needed**
13. **Pays a lot of attention to me**
14. **Goes out of her/ his way to hurt my feelings**
15. Forgets important things I think s(he) should remember
16. **Makes me feel disliked if I misbehave**
17. **Makes me feel what I do is important**
18. **Frightens or threatens me when I do something wrong**
19. **Cares about what I think, and likes me to talk about it**
20. Feels other children are better than I am no matter what I do
21. **Lets me know I am not wanted**
22. **Lets me know s(he) cares about me**
23. **Pays no attention to me as long as I do nothing to bother her/him**
24. **Treats me gently and with kindness**

Bold items indicate the items those were selected in the Japanese shortened version